

Great Pyramids of Kentucky Addendum

Implications for Diffusionist search for pre-Columbian Christians

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The Broaddus site, as discussed in my last paper (Great Pyramids of Kentucky: Constellation Alignments in the Broaddus (Ft. Ancient) Site, ResearchGate, September 2018), shows interesting constellation alignments. In the pursuit of discovering those alignments, Giza and Caracol (Belize) were cross referenced for well known Orion or Cygnus configuration sites. In the course of that exercise, the Bauval 11,000 BCE alignment was verified, but at the same time Orion was precluded from being the source of inspiration for the Fort Ancient (1200-1300 CE) site.

Orion Variances by Site | Sf. R. Careaga

Orion Configurations; left is Broaddus, center is Giza, and right is Caracol (Mayan)

By contrast, the alignment with Cygnus was shown within reasonable error margins (8% or less). Furthermore, the nearby mounds to the west of Zone 1 proved to be the y shaped Lyra constellation.

Additionally, two intriguing aspects of the Zone 1 Broaddus site pyramids were noted.

1. The presence of an awen shaped earthwork roughly half the size of Eagle Mound (OH), And in the same NW-SE alignment as other Rock Art sites.
2. The unusual lengthening of the northwest and southeast “limbs” of the Cygnus constellation. That is: they are in line but not in proportion to the northeast and southwest limbs.

The implication seems unambiguous for the diffusion theory of settlement: the pre-Columbian presence of Christians in Kentucky.

However, before we accept this we must object to two alternative diffusion-catastrophist hypotheses, as well as one mainstream archaeological (and historically relevant) hypothesis.

Plasmaglyph-Younger Dryas Theory

Recently, a discovery of a comet strike site in Greenland has provided correlative evidence for the

Tiamat/Atlantean (mid-Atlantic Ridge), and Delaware story of the end of the Ice Age. Peter Jungo-Mupp has provided evidence of the 1491 CE Melbourne comet (Ancient Destructions, episode 3 Mega Tsunami Melbourne – 1500 A.D. DVD) as well as Tunguska for being electrical. Electrical cometology is the hallmark aspect of the discussion in my paper, “Plasma Petroglyphs, Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction.” (uky.academia.edu/shifucareaga, 2018). In particular, the discussion of multiple worldwide motifs contain in the Part Two (pp. 38-79), Three (pp. 83-104), and in the Plates in Appendix B (pp. 139-158) provide a background, and I must refer people to that paper.

**Great Pyramids of KY with Cygnus/Lyra overlay,
Bluegrass Army Depot, Madison County,
Credit: KY From Above/Author**

According to this theory, (we shall call it the *Peratt-Talbott-Thornhill hypothesis*, *Ibid.* pp. 177-183), glyph shapes, even as large as entire earthworks (Nazca, Newark, England, etc..) are seen in the sky on account of the previous age of the “gods” (and heroes) being the result of solar system catastrophism. The argument here is that extremely powerful events, the kind that can sink Atlantis, Doggerland, Sundaland, Mu, Zealandia, etc... as well as melt the ice sheets and end megafauna proliferation - selectively - are the result of the breakup of a previous alignment of the solar system (Electrothermal Vine Hypothesis, “Plasma Electromagnetic Sky,” Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, pp. 20-22). The total evidence for this is too lengthy to go into here, but it starts with Earth’s very tilt and the moon’s evidence (*Ibid.*, M Plates, *Ibid.* pp.159-176).

suggesting one of two things: either the stars are moved, or in fact the overlay used in Figure 34 [bottom-right] is off 3°, *Ibid.* pp. 31)

According to native Americans, these events were particularly pronounced here in America (and Russia) where the event seems to have started. The Ohio Leo petroglyphs are squat, while the further west or south the glyphs are, the longer they get. Thunderbirds in the western US are impressive, but not quite as much as the Hummingbird earthwork of the Nazca or Paracas (Plasmaglyphs, *Ibid.*, L Plates and S Plates, also pp. 12-15, 59, 128).

The main point is that these glyphs were seen, literally, worldwide. They are even found in ancient Egypt, Rongorongo, and Chinese characters. There are stories in Sumer-Babylon and China that speak of the falling of the sky and the “creation of Heaven and Earth.” (see: Epic of Gilgamesh)

Vertical Broaddus with Cygnus Overlay
(“one may be interested now to know the ratios A/B and C/D are 68.75% and 62.98%, respectively. But while this skewing seems a bit odd, the angles A>B and C>D are both 3°,

Great Man, as a Plasma Thunderbolt (note the glyph depictions bottom-right on stone)

So it is entirely possible that the Broaddus site is an ancient astronomical site, or a memory site, which is recording important cultural glyphs from the past. For one, the Ft. Ancient culture appears to pay homage to the previous mound cultures. Just as the Mississippians appeared to try to revive the old religion of the Sun (actually a different star), and the “Hand” (or foot, or eagle wing) motif, and spiral (see: Moundville, AL), the Ft. Ancient created numerous sites which *do* reflect the Northern Isles’ own religious leanings, but do not appear to be militarily related. Though Ft. Ancient, OH appears to be an older site, it bears repeating that the name Fort

Ancient turned out to be a misnomer as the site is almost certainly not a fort in function. Other sites, such as “O’Bynum’s Fort” or “Portsmouth Earthworks” do not need to even be discussed, they bear little resemblance to defensible structures. They are, primarily geometric in function. Another function seems to be (post conjunction breakup) the recording of solar and lunar alignments.

Zone 1 close:up, awen earthwork; credit: KFA/author

Many of these sites have dating similar to events in China where the emperor illogically calls for re-measuring the solstices and equinoxes, as the seasons were apparently “thrown into disarray.” Almost certainly if uniformitarianism were correct, farmers would know

and pass down extremely accurate information and would not need government assistance in this matter.

Is it possible, then, that multiple people (without diffusion), in multiple continents (if they were not approaching civilization the same way as Europe, India, or China), tried to revitalize the ancient religion? Consider the cult of Amun-Re, or Horus, and you will see it is more than possible. The awen glyph, as analyzed, could very well have been the conjunction of Mars-Venus, Earth, and the Moon (or Jupiter). Kentucky sites and Newspaper Rock, UT, seem to indicate a fascinating milieu of astronomical recordings taking place during a transition period of the gods. For more discussion on the gods being planets, I must refer the reader to the diligent analysis of Dwardu Cardona, who attacks this problem vigorously. (“God Star,” 2006)

The Native Hypothesis

Although it is not readily clear what the native Kentucky population was, or what interest they would have in the Northern Cross, let alone in Lyra or the awen glyph, based on the above the discussion the argument could be made that as all the world’s religions are related to the Tepe to Transition Period events (see Table 1 in my paper, “On the Origins of Religions”, 2018, pp. 1-3) then really any interest could have been possible. Is it not also possible that a new catastrophic event was noted in the general vicinity of the constellation Cygnus, and bore memorialization? Considering the local village under excavation and is relatively small and obscure, it appears unlikely they would have the manpower, or need, to do this; literally most subsistence societies do not have the spare calories. More likely than not, the agricultural location was selected due to proximity with the site. Since the mounds cannot and have not been excavated, being located on the federally sensitive Bluegrass Army Depot, it’s entirely possible that the mounds are much older. The choosing of this location for the army

base seems to support Rick Osman's ("Graves of the Golden Bear") hypothesis that an early American coverup of *anything* that might be construed as pre-American/pioneer claims was a motivation. Whatever the case may be, the site is thoroughly protected from archaeologists and the public alike. The army may have conducted its own internal investigations, but not in some time, because the mounds are thoroughly covered by aged trees. According to LiDAR and sat views, the very road layout of the base has been altered to accommodate the location. Clearly they thought it important enough to not use the dirt as construction filler. Could the aboriginal American Indians have revered the Northern Cross as well? Absolutely. But as we don't know which tribe precisely would have been here, and records among tribes are speculative at best, and totally lost at worst (disease, warfare, intermingling of tribes, relocation, etc...), then we may never know the exact desires of the natives, be they pre-Cherokee or Phoenicians.

Right: LiDAR scans from Broaddus/B.A.D.; Credit: KFA

Early Christians? Welsh?

It seems almost certain to me that the continent has been a long established revolving door, which western European (Renaissance) consciousness discovered anew for itself, much as a teenager would "discover" Chuck Berry or Bob Marley. The fact is that certainly *some* travelers have been here, whether they be Chinese in 1432 (spreading smallpox by accident), the Vikings in the Sagas, or early Hebrews (Lost Ten Tribes theory). Recent research into the Shang dynasties connection to the Olmec shows some evidence that diffusion is almost certain. So we must, at the end, return to the Madoc hypothesis, which offers the most compelling evidence in the Ohio River Valley, but also in Illinois and Tennessee, etc... The presence of glyphs that are only meaningfully decipherable with Coelbren is well established ("Ancient Kentucke Inscriptions: Prince Madoc, Fact or Fiction," J Michael, 2004). However, does that mean that the Broaddus Site is Welsh "Indians"?

The proximity of it to the Berea Indianfort (and other research sites under way by AKHA) is one clue. Another is the obviously lengthened "vertical" section of the Northern Cross" and with an awen earthwork in tandem, almost as if a stamp to say "we were here."

Of course, as per the Plasmaglyphs hypothesis, the awen may be referring to some conjunction in which case the genius astronomer engineers of this site have told us in what "house" the conjunction was to be seen and where it must have fallen apart (*Religions*, Ibid. pp.40-43). As the crow flies, this site is approximately 32 miles from Nada Tunnel at the Red River Gorge, where numerous rockcliff art recordings are found (*Plasmaglyphs*, Ibid. pp. 31; *Religions*, pp. 2, 22-26). It is not impossible to imagine a tight network in this area, who utilized the Kentucky River and Red River as its byways to establish a civilization in the wilderness. The Gorge is one of many places (also Indianfort) where excellent astronomical observations could be made, despite the sea of trees in the bygone era.

What strikes the author, though are the firm carbon datings by archaeologist Dr. Kellie Carmean (EKU) which date this to precisely one of the two disputed eras of the Madoc hypothesis. Even if the site is older, it is almost certainly not older than 500 CE, when the second "revival" wave of mound-building in the Ohio River Valley began (Ibid. Table 1, pp. 7 is not a complete list, there are more).

Conclusions

In the author's opinion, none of the hypotheses can be directly proven or disproven without on site excavation which isn't bound to happen for at least the next ten to twenty years. Mostly because the base is still technically under operation. But also because of NAGPRA, which will be almost certainly used by either the establishment, tribes, or both, in order to prevent exploration. For now, archaeo-astronomy holds our key. In particular the method I outlined of ratio comparisons, which, when used in comparison with various sites, may in fact give us excellent results. In a future paper on all the [known] pyramids (conical or platform) in Kentucky (*Plasmaglyphs*, Ibid. pp. 95, 99), I will explore the relationships of this site to Cygnus in greater

precision as far as dating, to try to find an AD alignment that better fits than 1000 CE. BCE Cygnus alignments may exist which fit better, but it seems unlikely to be recent, and as these are dirt mounds, they do not seem to extend back very far. One era that might be of use is the Poverty Point dating period, which as it happens, is also a Plasmaglyph motif site I have discussed in the aforementioned paper.

If there is a correlation there, it may support the Catastrophist/Solar System realignment hypothesis further. One thing to note is that in doing so it doesn't necessarily constrain the diffusionist hypothesis at all. As we are aware the Sea Peoples are confirmed diffusionists who were escaping catastrophe, as were the Amalekites (Hyksos). And based on the Welsh hypothesis, an electro-comet disaster in southern Britannia may have indeed been cause for wide diffusion. It's easy to see that the hypothesis can marry and merge, and that would not at all be surprising.

"Extraordinary claims require extraordinary evidence." As far as the author is concerned the idea that people did not seek new hunting grounds or lands (or only did so how "the establishment" says so) is an extraordinary claim contrary to recorded history and archaeological record (see: Sumer-Gobekli Tepe, and Indo-European linguistics).

Evidence of Chinese even in New Zealand 7,000 years ago has emerged ("Skeletons in the Cupboard, Ep. 2: Under the Carpet", YouTube), as well as Egyptian hieroglyphs in Australia! Diffusion is not a hypothesis it is the norm, and the rule, even according to the mainstream. After all, the Beringia hypothesis is a diffusionist process, as is settling Central America after South America. [And Greenland crater and the Dead Sea sites are catastrophist!]

So the argument that the site is purely native, purely culturally isolated (given the ORV-South America connections, *Plasmaglyphs* Ibid. pp. 13, *Religions* Ibid. Table 5, Appendix B) seems untenable. It would require extra evidence, and right now only one person has had access to the site. Her analysis focus is almost exclusively on flint and pottery. So nothing definitive can be said for *nor against* the Welsh (or any other) hypothesis regarding the Great Pyramids of Kentucky.